

FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN PRIMARY STUDENTS THROUGH SECONDARY USE OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE.

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the pedagogical foundations of the formation of ecological culture in primary school students through the secondary use of household waste. In the modern education system, the issue of environmental education has gained urgent importance, and one of the important tasks is the development of a conscious attitude to nature in students. The article analyzes ways to develop students' ecological knowledge, skills and competencies through waste sorting, recycling and their use for creative and practical purposes. Also, effective methods of forming ecological culture in primary school classes using interactive methods and practical tasks are considered. The use of secondary raw materials provides the opportunity to develop thrift, responsibility, a conscious attitude to nature conservation and creative qualities in students.

Keywords: ecological culture, primary school, household waste, secondary use, recycling, environmental education, environmental education, nature protection, interactive methods, practical activities, thrift, creativity, sustainable development, environmental awareness.

Introduction. In today's globalization process, environmental problems, in particular, the issue of household waste management, are gaining relevance worldwide. As a result of population growth, accelerated urbanization processes and changes in consumer culture, the volume of household waste is increasing sharply. This leads to environmental pollution, depletion of natural resources and disruption of the ecological balance. Therefore, reducing waste, sorting it and establishing a secondary recycling system are important tasks not only from an economic, but also from a pedagogical and educational perspective.

Ensuring ecological safety and environmental protection in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of state policy. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Environmental Protection" (adopted in a new edition in 2019) and the Law "On Waste" (2018) establish the legal framework for the collection, transportation, processing and disposal of waste. These documents state that ensuring ecological safety, reducing waste and developing a recycling system are the common tasks of the state and citizens. Also, the decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the field of ecology and environmental protection pay special attention to increasing ecological culture, improving the ecological literacy of the population, and educating the younger generation in the spirit of a conscious attitude towards nature. In particular, the "Environmental Protection Concept until 2030" identifies improving the environmental education system and forming an environmental culture in educational institutions as one of the priority tasks.

In the field of education, great attention is also paid to the development of environmental education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (new edition of 2020) and the "National Program for Personnel Training" define the formation of environmental awareness, a careful attitude to nature, and practical environmental skills in students as an important component of the educational process. Especially in the primary school stage, environmental education is of great importance in forming a culture of love for nature, its preservation, and rational use of resources in children.

From this point of view, the formation of an environmental culture in primary school students through the secondary use of household waste is a pressing pedagogical problem. Because the reuse

of waste and its use in various educational and practical activities develops not only environmental knowledge in students, but also creativity, thrift, and a sense of responsibility. Such an approach serves to connect the educational process with life and strengthen the environmental awareness of students through practical activities.

Therefore, the introduction of technologies for the secondary use of household waste in the formation of environmental culture in primary school students is one of the important pedagogical tasks of today, which serves to form an environmentally sustainable society.

The process of forming an ecological culture in primary school students should be organized taking into account their age and psychological characteristics. At this stage, children develop a positive attitude towards nature, a sense of responsibility for its preservation, and initial ideas about environmental problems. In particular, teaching through the secondary use of household waste (upcycling) is one of the most effective practical areas of environmental education.

Household waste is plastic, paper, glass, metal, and organic waste generated in everyday life, and by reusing or converting them into secondary products, it is possible to reduce the negative impact on the environment. For primary school students, this process is not only a source of environmental knowledge, but also a field of creative activity. Because in the process of making various items from waste, children simultaneously develop both nature conservation and creative skills.

In the pedagogical process, the organization of secondary use of household waste is carried out in several stages. At the first stage, students are given basic knowledge about waste types, their impact on nature, and sorting rules. At this stage, the teacher uses explanatory, conversational, and demonstration methods. At the second stage, students are involved in practical activities, completing small projects on sorting waste and making simple items from it. At the third stage, students' creative work is analyzed and ecological conclusions are drawn.

The use of interactive methods in primary grades increases the effectiveness of forming an ecological culture. For example, using the "Brainstorming" method, students think about what new items can be made from waste. Using the "Cluster" method, waste types and ways to recycle them are systematized. Based on the "Project-based learning" technology, students work in small groups and perform practical work, such as making flower pots from plastic bottles, paper decorations, or toys from cardboard boxes.

Also, through the "Fish Skeleton" or "Why?" methods, students develop the ability to analyze the causes and consequences of environmental problems. For example, based on the question "Why should we not throw waste into nature?", Children develop environmental awareness by thinking. This strengthens their critical thinking and environmental responsibility.

Didactic games also play an important role in the process of secondary use of household waste. For example, through games such as "Sort and Find", "Place Correctly", "Ecological Detective", students strengthen their skills in the correct separation and use of waste. Such games form environmental knowledge in children in an interesting and memorable way.

Practical observations show that the creative use of waste develops not only environmental knowledge in students, but also hard work, thrift, responsibility and teamwork skills. For example, during the lesson, students learn the culture of helping each other, exchanging ideas, and achieving a common result when working in groups.

In addition, the effectiveness of education increases when environmental projects are organized in collaboration with parents. The involvement of parents in the process of sorting waste at home, reusing it, and making ecological products helps to form strong ecological habits in children. This ensures the continuity of ecological education.

The formation of ecological culture in primary school students through the secondary use of household waste connects the educational process with life, develops the practical and creative activities of students, and strengthens their ecological awareness and responsibility. This approach serves to ensure that the future generation has a conscious, careful, and responsible attitude towards nature.

The secondary use of household waste is of particular importance as an important didactic tool in the process of forming ecological culture in primary school students. Because this approach allows students to understand environmental problems not only theoretically, but also through direct practical activities. Observations show that when children work with real materials, a careful attitude towards nature is formed faster and ecological concepts are mastered more firmly.

Tasks based on the reuse of waste increase the activity of students and encourage them to think independently. For example, in the process of creating new educational tools or decorative items from discarded materials, children develop not only creativity, but also the ability to appreciate resources. This serves to form a conscious attitude, which is the main goal of environmental education.

Also, the fact that students work in groups during practical classes has a positive effect on the development of their cooperation and communication skills. Jointly implemented environmental projects form in children the ability to feel responsibility, distribute tasks and achieve a common result. This process strengthens environmental culture not only as an individual, but also as a social skill.

Practical activities with an ecological content enliven the lesson process and increase interest in students. However, in some cases, factors such as a lack of materials or limited lesson time may prevent the full implementation of such activities. Therefore, the teacher should focus on using simple and convenient materials based on the existing conditions. Another important aspect is that the process of forming an ecological culture should be continuous. One-time classes do not give sufficient results, on the contrary, through regularly repeated practical work, stable ecological habits are formed in students. This indicates the need for a systematic organization of the educational process.

Conclusion. This article analyzes the issue of forming an ecological culture in primary school students through the secondary use of household waste. Studies show that an approach based on practical activities in the process of environmental education positively changes students' attitudes towards nature and strengthens their ecological knowledge. Tasks and creative activities focused on recycling waste serve to develop important qualities in students, such as observation, creativity, responsibility, and thrift. In particular, the process of working with real materials develops in children the skills of understanding environmental problems and a conscious approach to their solutions.

Also, practical exercises with ecological content help to organize the lesson process in an interesting and effective way, ensuring the active participation of students. This confirms the importance of environmental education not only theoretically, but also practically. In general, the formation of an ecological culture based on the secondary use of household waste is one of the effective pedagogical directions at the primary education stage, which serves to develop environmental awareness and responsibility in the future generation.

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